

Anxiety Levels Among Undergraduate Nursing Students Prior to their First Clinical Placement in Govt. Colleges of Nursing, Peshawar

¹Maria Yousaf, ²Sabahat Yousaf, ³Mehwish Pervaiz, ⁴Uzma Basir, ⁵Uzma Rafique
¹⁻⁵Govt. College of Nursing at Lady Reading Hospital, Peshawar Khyber Pakhtunkhwa,
Pakistan

^{*}ktkmariayousaf@gmail.com ^{*}sabahatyousaf123456@gmail.com,

³meshok842@gmail.com, ⁴mk5318475@gmail.com, ⁵uzmarafique657@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Sabahat Yousaf

sabahatyousaf123456@gmail.com

Maria Yousaf

ktkmariayousaf@gmail.com

Abstract

Introduction: The clinical learning environment is a complex social entity that influences student competency within the clinical setting. Anxiety contributes to a student's performance in the clinical setting because it initiates the fight-or-flight response leading to a positive or negative outcome. Aim: The study was aimed to assess the level of anxiety among nursing students during the initial clinical experience. Methodology: A non-experimental descriptive survey was adopted for the study. The sample of the study consists of 132 final year nursing students who were selected using a convenient sample technique. Demographic Performa and Zung Self-Rating Anxiety Scale were used to collect the data. Results: Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data. The analysis revealed that 81.1% of the students were having a normal range of anxiety whereas while (15.9%) had experienced mild to moderate anxiety levels, and only (3%) had severe anxiety, with a Mean \pm SD of (1.22 \pm 0.49). The Chi-square test showed that no significant association was found between anxiety and selected demographic variables. Conclusion: The findings revealed that the teaching and training given to the students before the clinical experience was adequate and appropriate.

Chapter #1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Anxiety is a feeling of nervousness or unease that can significantly impact one's life in various ways. It can be triggered by internal and external factors⁽¹⁾. Unlike fear, which is a response to a clear threat, anxiety is characterized by an inexplicable sense of unease or fear defined by American Psychiatric Association⁽²⁾. Additionally, anxiety differs from stress, which is a normal part of life and not inherently good or bad. Approximately 1 in 5 young people experience anxiety, which can affect the body, feelings, thoughts, and actions⁽¹⁾. Anxiety affects everyone differently⁽³⁾. For nursing students, the clinical area is particularly daunting due to its unfamiliarity⁽⁴⁾. During their first clinical experience, students often feel anxious due to fear of evaluation, unfamiliar surroundings, lack of practice, and fear of mistakes⁽⁵⁾. Nursing students experience high levels of anxiety when providing patient care, leading to decreased learning, compromised patient care, and diminished confidence⁽⁶⁾. Clinical practice is essential for nursing and medical students, enabling them to apply theoretical knowledge to real-life situations and develop critical thinking skills to solve problems⁽⁷⁾. Research indicates that nursing students in the United States frequently experience anxiety during clinical training, with higher anxiety levels compared to other students, particularly in clinical settings versus classrooms. Studies conducted in the US between the late 1980s and mid-1990s identified numerous obstacles faced by students in new clinical settings⁽⁸⁾. In Pakistan there is lack of research to assess the level of anxiety among nursing students therefore, it is crucial to investigate the causes of clinical anxiety and develop strategies to mitigate it facilitating students' progression into confident, skilled practitioners⁽⁹⁾.

1.2 Background Study

Anxiety in clinical settings poses a significant challenge for nursing students, impacting their ability to engage safely and compassionately with clients, which can, in turn, affect their academic performance and physical and mental well-being⁽⁸⁾. High levels of stress and anxiety during clinical training can impair students' psychomotor skills and decision-making abilities, thus interfering with patient care⁽⁶⁾. Recognizing this, nurse educators must focus on helping students manage anxiety to foster a safer, more supportive learning environment⁽⁸⁾. Research has shown that students experiencing excessive anxiety frequently lack confidence and fear making mistakes. This apprehension is particularly evident in high-stress areas like maternal-child care, where students may feel additional pressure due to the sensitive nature of patient interactions. Simulation exercises have been introduced to help mitigate this anxiety by providing students with hands-on experience before they enter real clinical environments, although responses to simulation vary among students⁽⁶⁾.

One common area where nursing students experience anxiety is in caring for elderly patients, often due to misconceptions and lack of experience. Many students feel uncertain about their ability to communicate effectively and provide care for older adults. A pilot study assessing nursing students' perceptions of elderly care, as well as their anxiety levels before and after a clinical rotation in a long-term care facility, highlighted the importance of supportive educational interventions. Findings from such studies inform future program designs to help students manage anxiety and build confidence in providing care for diverse patient populations⁽¹⁰⁾. Clinical internships are fundamental to nursing students' professional growth, bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application. These internships shape students' professional identities and prepare them for the realities of nursing. However, this period is also marked by various anxiety-inducing factors, including fear of mistakes, encountering end-of-life situations, and managing relationships with clinical staff⁽¹¹⁾. The first clinical practicum, in particular, is often the most stressful phase of a nursing student's training, as they adapt to a new environment and face the demands of professional care⁽⁷⁾. Creating a structured, supportive clinical learning environment, with clear role definitions, active learning opportunities, and thorough supervision, is essential in helping students cope with these challenges and achieve clinical learning objectives⁽¹²⁾.

The clinical learning environment itself is crucial to a successful nursing education, providing students with opportunities to apply theoretical knowledge and develop problem-solving and critical-thinking skills. In an ideal environment, students are supported in gaining both theoretical knowledge and practical competencies⁽⁹⁾. Such environments also encourage students to participate actively in their learning, ensuring they are well-prepared to enter the healthcare field. A positive clinical setting is designed not only to teach nursing skills but also to shape the future of nursing professionals by fostering confidence and competence⁽⁷⁾. The adverse effects of anxiety on health and academic performance are well documented. For nursing students, stress often peaks during clinical placements, where a lack of preparedness, fear of making errors, and unfamiliarity with hospital protocols can exacerbate anxiety⁽¹²⁾. Interventions like reflective journaling and mentoring can help students better navigate these challenges, allowing them to process their experiences and focus on continuous improvement in a supportive atmosphere⁽¹³⁾.

For example, mental health rotations are an area in which reflective practices, such as journaling, can play a crucial role. These rotations help students build positive attitudes toward mental health care and develop a genuine interest in the field. Reflective journaling, specifically, allows students to record their experiences, identify areas for growth, and gain insights into caring for individuals with mental health challenges. Such practices not only reduce anxiety during clinical placements

but also enhance students' skills in mental health care⁽¹³⁾. Additionally, the transition from adolescence to adulthood can compound anxiety for many students as they navigate increased responsibilities. First-year nursing students, in particular, face the dual challenge of adapting to a rigorous academic environment and meeting the intellectual and social demands of professional training. During this time, depression, anxiety, and stress are common, further complicating students' adjustment to clinical practice⁽¹⁴⁾. Ultimately, while clinical experience is essential in nursing education, it is consistently associated with increased anxiety that may impact learning outcomes. Studies show that nursing students often experience mild to moderate levels of anxiety due to a lack of coping mechanisms, which can diminish the overall quality of their learning experience⁽⁵⁾. By addressing these issues through structured support systems and a well-designed clinical environment, educators can help nursing students build the resilience and skills they need to become competent and confident practitioners, enhancing their academic success and professional development⁽¹⁾.

1.3 Rational of the Study

This study focuses on assessing anxiety levels among final-year BS Nursing students before their first clinical placement in government colleges of nursing in Peshawar. Using the Zung Self-Rating Anxiety Scale, it aims to quantify the anxiety levels and examine relationships with demographic variables, such as age, gender, and prior healthcare exposure. The study will provide crucial insights into how anxiety manifests in Pakistani nursing students, offering an evidence base to develop tailored interventions for anxiety reduction. The rationale for this research stems from the vital role clinical placements play in nursing education. These placements not only bridge theoretical learning with practical application but also serve as foundational experiences for professional growth. Addressing and mitigating anxiety during this phase can enhance students' learning outcomes, confidence, and readiness for future clinical roles, ultimately contributing to the development of skilled, confident nursing professionals in Pakistan.

1.4 Objective of the Study

The objective of this study is:

- To assess the level of anxiety among final-year BS Nursing student before their first clinical placement experience.
- To examine the relationship between anxiety and selected demographic variables among final-year BS Nursing students before their first clinical placement.

1.5 Operational Definitions

Anxiety; A sense of apprehension or anxiety regarding something with an uncertain outcome.

Level of anxiety: The score obtained from the Zung-Self Rating Anxiety Scale ranging from 20 – 80

20 – 44: Normal (no Anxiety)

45 – 59: Mild Anxiety

60 – 74: Moderate Anxiety

75 – 80: Severe Anxiety

Undergraduate Nursing Student: Students currently enrolled in Bachelor of Science in nursing program, with no prior clinical placement experience.

Clinical Placement: is a practical training program where students apply their theoretical knowledge and gain hands-on experience in their field of study.

1.6 Summary

The introduction of the thesis highlights the significance of anxiety among nursing students, particularly during their first clinical placement experience. Anxiety can hinder students' ability to engage effectively with patients, negatively impacting both their academic performance and personal well-being. The introduction outlines the factors contributing to anxiety, including fear of making mistakes, unfamiliar environments, and lack of experience, which are prevalent during clinical training. The chapter also discusses the importance of addressing anxiety through educational interventions such as simulation exercises, reflective journaling, and structured clinical environments. The research aims to assess the anxiety levels of final-year BS Nursing students in Peshawar before their first clinical placement, contributing to a better understanding of this issue and identifying strategies to improve student outcomes in clinical settings.

Chapter No 02: Review Of Literature

The issue of clinical anxiety among nursing students has been extensively explored in the literature, with studies highlighting its prevalence, impacts, and potential interventions. Research from the late 20th century identified strategies such as minimizing the interval between orientation and clinical rotations, providing patient assignments in advance, and using guided imagery to alleviate anxiety⁽¹⁵⁾. While these methods have proven effective in reducing stress during clinical placements, their applicability to modern nursing students—primarily from the Millennial and Generation Z cohorts—may be limited due to generational differences in learning preferences and coping mechanisms⁽⁸⁾. These students, accustomed to technological connectivity and multitasking, require tailored strategies to address their unique challenges in clinical environments. Despite the critical impact of anxiety on learning outcomes and clinical performance, a comprehensive review of strategies targeting these generational groups' remains underexplored⁽¹⁶⁾.

Clinical anxiety in nursing education stems from multiple factors, including fears of being observed, apprehension about evaluations, and concerns about making

mistakes. High anxiety levels can impair cognitive function, reduce motivation, and hinder decision-making, thereby affecting students' academic and clinical performance⁽¹⁾. Evidence suggests that active participation in patient care enhances confidence and competence, but these benefits are often compromised by elevated anxiety⁽⁴⁾. Simulation workshops have been found to temporarily reduce pre-clinical anxiety, although the persistence of these benefits during initial clinical encounters is unclear. Additionally, students often report a lack of confidence in communication and physical assessment skills before their first clinical rotation, both of which are essential for patient-centred care and building trust⁽⁶⁾. Experiential learning is central to the development of clinical competence in nursing students. Classroom, laboratory, and simulation settings provide opportunities to practice and validate skills under instructor supervision before entering real-world clinical environments⁽⁹⁾. Early exposure to patient care is crucial for reducing anxiety and bridging the gap between theory and practice. However, clinical placements often induce significant stress due to unfamiliar settings, challenging schedules, and interpersonal dynamics with clinical staff⁽¹⁰⁾. Research has classified this anxiety into state and trait anxiety, with state anxiety being a temporary response to external triggers. Addressing these triggers through structured preparation, such as small-group tutorials involving students, clinical mentors, and lecturers, has proven effective in easing transitions into clinical practice and improving student confidence⁽⁷⁾.

The global nursing shortage has further emphasized the need to address anxiety in nursing education. Clinical internships play a critical role in shaping students' professional identities and ensuring a smooth transition into clinical roles. Extended internships, especially those lasting six months or longer, have been shown to significantly influence students' decisions to remain in the profession⁽¹¹⁾. However, these periods are also marked by heightened mental health challenges, including anxiety and depression, which can negatively affect academic performance, personal well-being, and career aspirations⁽¹⁴⁾. International studies reveal that the prevalence of depression among nursing students ranges from 10% to 85%, highlighting the psychological challenges they face during clinical placements. Addressing these issues is imperative to improve learning outcomes and long-term career satisfaction⁽⁹⁾. Simulation-based learning has emerged as a valuable tool for reducing clinical anxiety by allowing students to practice skills in a controlled environment. Simulations replicate real-world scenarios, providing a safe space for students to make mistakes and learn without the immediate pressures of patient care⁽⁶⁾. Over the past two decades, patient simulation has gained popularity in healthcare education, with evidence suggesting it can replace up to 50% of traditional clinical practice while maintaining or improving learning outcomes⁽¹⁴⁾. This method is particularly beneficial for Millennial and Generation Z students, who thrive in technology-rich

environments⁽⁸⁾. However, while simulations can significantly reduce pre-clinical anxiety, their ability to address the stress experienced during actual clinical encounters requires further investigation⁽¹²⁾.

Supportive clinical environments are vital for enhancing student learning and reducing anxiety⁽⁹⁾. Mentorship and collaboration with clinical staff provide students with guidance and constructive feedback, helping them navigate the complexities of real-world healthcare settings⁽⁷⁾. Effective communication within the clinical environment fosters trust and confidence, enabling students to focus on skill development and patient care⁽¹⁶⁾. Structured preparation, including orientation programs and mentorship, is particularly important during initial placements when anxiety levels are highest. Such interventions not only reduce stress but also improve students' satisfaction with their clinical experiences, influencing their professional attitudes and career commitment⁽⁷⁾. In countries like Taiwan and China, where nursing education includes extended clinical practicums, students face additional challenges such as balancing academic demands with clinical responsibilities. These experiences often induce anxiety due to a lack of expertise and the dynamic nature of patient care⁽¹¹⁾. Research emphasizes the importance of supportive learning environments, structured preparation, and effective communication to mitigate these challenges⁽²⁾. In Taiwan, for instance, the Fundamental Nursing practicum represents students' first exposure to clinical skills, making it a critical period for building confidence and competence⁽¹¹⁾. Mentorship and structured learning activities during this time have been shown to enhance student outcomes and reduce anxiety⁽¹⁾.

The negative effects of anxiety extend beyond academic and clinical performance, impacting students' mental health and long-term career trajectories⁽¹³⁾. Elevated anxiety levels can lead to dissatisfaction with the clinical learning environment, which is a significant determinant of professional attitudes and retention in the nursing profession. Dissatisfied students are less likely to remain in the field, making it imperative for educators to create positive and supportive clinical experiences⁽¹⁷⁾. By addressing the emotional and psychological aspects of clinical training, educators can foster environments that enhance learning, build resilience, and prepare students to thrive in complex healthcare systems⁽⁴⁾.

Ultimately, the goal of nursing education is to prepare students to navigate the challenges of an ever-changing healthcare environment. While experiential learning is essential for skill development, it often involves stress and anxiety that can hinder learning outcomes⁽¹⁶⁾. Simulation-based learning, mentorship, and supportive clinical environments are critical interventions for reducing anxiety and fostering confidence and competence⁽⁶⁾. Addressing the psychological needs of nursing students not only enhances their clinical performance but also equips them to succeed as future healthcare professionals⁽¹⁸⁾.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

3.1 Study Design

A descriptive cross-sectional study design was used to examine anxiety levels among final year BS nursing students before their first clinical placement experience in Govt. Colleges of Nursing, Peshawar. A cross-sectional approach enables data collection from a representative sample at a single point in time.

3.1.1 Study Settings

The study was conducted at Govt. College of Nursing at Khyber Teaching Hospital (KTH), Hayatabad Medical Complex (HMC) and Lady Reading Hospital in Peshawar.

3.1.2 Study Duration

The study was conducted over a period of 4 months. This included time for preparation, data collection, analysis, and reporting.

3.2 Sample Size

A sample size of 132 final-year nursing students was targeted. Based on the number of final year nursing students at Govt. College of Nursing at KTH, HMC and LRH hospitals which is total 200 students, the sample size was determined using the Rao soft sample size calculator, a sample size of 132 was determined, accounting for a 50% response distribution, a 5% margin of error, and a 95% confidence level.

3.3 Sampling Technique

Convenient sampling technique were used to collect data from Govt. College of Nursing at KTH, HMC and LRH hospitals.

3.4 Sample Selection

3.4.1 Inclusion Criteria

- Final year BS Nursing students of the 8th semester in GCON at KTH, HMC and LRH Peshawar
- About to experience their first clinical placement
- Willing to participate and provide informed consent

3.4.2 Exclusion Criteria

- Students who have already completed their first clinical placement.
- Students of 7th semester of final year Students who are not willing to participate or provide informed consent

3.5 Data Collection Tool

Data was collected using the Zung Self-Rating Anxiety Scale and Demographic Performa.

Part-I: Demographic Performa: This tool consists of 11 items seeking information about- gender, age, residence, course, family type, sibling, religion, income per month, clinical experience, and experience of caring for the sick in the family and relatives in the medical field.

Part- II: Zung Self-Rating Anxiety Scale (SAS): This self-report scale was developed by Zung MD (1929-1992) and consists of 20 items, 15 positively and 5 negatively stated items. The participants' responses are categorized into A little of the time, some of the time, Good part of the time, and Most of the time. The maximum total score is 80. The negatively stated items were scored reversely. The test-retest reliability of the tool was found to be 0.91. The Cronbach's alpha was found to be 0.89.

3.6 Data Collection Procedure

Before data collection, informed consent was obtained from participants. Approval for data collection was granted by the Government College of Nursing at Lady Reading Hospital, Peshawar. Additionally, permission for access was secured from the respective principals at Hayatabad Medical Complex (HMC) and Khyber Teaching Hospital (KTH). Based on the determined sample size, questionnaires were distributed in the classroom setting. The collected data were subsequently compiled and prepared for analysis.

3.7 Data Analysis Procedure

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 26 for statistical analysis. The continuous variable, anxiety level, was measured using the Zung Self-Rating Anxiety Scale, while demographic variables were treated as categorical. Descriptive statistics were applied to summarize continuous data, whereas frequencies and percentages were calculated for categorical variables. To determine the association between anxiety levels and selected demographic variables, the Chi-square test was conducted, depending on the data distribution and sample size. All analysed data were presented in the form of graphs and tables for clear interpretation and visualization

Chapter 4: Results

4.1 Description of demographic variable of the study

Table 1: *Frequency And Percentage Of Demographic Variable Of The Sample*

Variables	Characteristic	Frequency=N	Percentage
Gender	Male	N=66	50%
	Female	N=66	50%
area of residence	Home	N=45	34%
	Hostel	N=87	66%
	paying guest	N=0	0%
name of institute	HMC	N=33	25%
	LRH	N=33	25%
	KTH	N=66	50%
type of family	nuclear family	N=68	52%
	joint family	N=64	48%
Religion	Christian	N=10	8%
	Hindu	N=2	2%

	Muslim	N=120	91%
	Other	N=0	0%
number of sibling	None	N=3	2%
	One	N=3	2%
	Two	N=14	11%
	three and above	N=112	85%
monthly income of the family	less than ten thousand	N=2	2%
	ten thousand to twenty thousand	N=7	5%
	twenty to thirty thousands	N=21	16%
	greater than thirty thousands	N=102	77%
no of days of clinical experience	one month	N=7	5%
	two months	N=53	40%
	greater than three months	N=72	55%
experience caring for the sick	Home	N=18	14%
	Hospital	N=114	86%
do you have any close relative working in medical nursing profession	Yes	N=76	58%
	No	N=56	42%
age category	below 22	N=34	26%
	22 to30	N=98	74%
	above 31	N=0	0%

The study results revealed the following demographic characteristics (see Table 1): the sample comprised an equal number of females (50%, N = 66) and males (50%, N = 66), with the gender ratio being consistent across all selected institutes. Regarding residence, 34% (N = 45) lived at home, while 66% (N = 87) resided in hostels. Concerning the institutes, half of the participants (50%) were from the College of Nursing at Khyber Teaching Hospital, while 25% (N = 33) each were from the College of Nursing at Lady Reading Hospital and the College of Nursing at Hayatabad Medical Complex. In terms of religion, the majority of participants (91%, N = 120) were Muslim, 8% (N = 10) were Christian, and 2% (N = 2) were Hindu. Regarding family structure, 58% (N = 68) of participants lived in nuclear families, while 48% (N = 64) lived in joint families. In terms of siblings, 2% (N = 3) had no siblings, 2% (N = 3) had one sibling, 11% (N = 14) had two siblings, and 85% (N = 112) had three or more siblings.

The participants' household incomes varied, with 2% (N = 2) earning below Rs. 10,000 per month, 5% (N = 7) earning between Rs. 10,000 and Rs. 20,000 per month, 16% (N = 21) earning between Rs. 20,000 and Rs. 30,000 per month, and the majority (77%, N = 102) earning more than Rs. 30,000 per month. Regarding clinical experience, 5% (N = 7) had one month of clinical experience, 40% (N = 53) had two months, and 55% (N = 72) had more than three months of experience. In terms of experience caring for the sick, the majority (86%, N = 114) had experience in hospital settings, while 14% (N = 18) had cared for the sick at home. Additionally, most participants (58%, N = 76) reported having relatives working in the medical field, while 42% (N = 58) did not. Regarding age distribution, most participants (74%, N = 98) were aged between 20 and 30 years, while 26% (N = 34) were below 20 years of age.

4.2 Level of Anxiety

Table 2: *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Responses to the 20 Items of the Zung Self-Rating Anxiety Scale Among Undergraduate Nursing Students*

		Mean	Frequency =N	percentage %
Idno		67		
i feel more nervous and anxious than usual	a little of the time		62	47.0%
	some of the time		54	40.9%
	good part of the time		3	2.3%
	most of the time		13	9.8%
i feel afraid for no reason at all	a little of the time		77	58.3%
	some of the time		37	28.0%
	good part of the time		15	11.4%
	most of the time		3	2.3%
i get upset easily or feel panicky	a little of the time		58	43.9%
	some of the time		52	39.4%
	good part of the time		14	10.6%
	most of the time		8	6.1%
i feel like i am falling a part and going to pieces	a litthe time		70	53.0%
	some of the time		34	25.8%
	good part of the time		13	9.8%
	most of the time		15	11.4%
i feel that everything is	a little of the time		35	26.5%

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alright and nothing bad will happen	some of the time	41	31.1%
	good part of the time	26	19.7%
	most of the time	30	22.7%
my arms and legs shake and tremble	a little of the time	75	56.8%
	some of the time	40	30.3%
	good part of the time	12	9.1%
	most of the time	5	3.8%
i am bothered by headaches,neck and back pain	a little of the time	62	47.0%
	some of the time	44	33.3%
	good part of the time	18	13.6%
	most of the time	8	6.1%
i feel weak and get tired easily	a little of the time	52	39.4%
	some of the time	53	40.2%
	good part of the time	13	9.8%
	most of the time	14	10.6%
i feel calm and can set still easily	a little of the time	50	37.9%
	some of the time	41	31.1%
	good part of the time	26	19.7%
	most of the time	15	11.4%
i can feel my heart beating fast	a little of the time	55	41.7%
	some of the time	53	40.2%
	good part of the time	13	9.8%
	most of the time	11	8.3%
i am bothered by dizzy spells	a little of the time	71	53.8%
	some of the time	40	30.3%
	good part of the time	13	9.8%
	most of the time	8	6.1%
i have fainting spells or feel like it	a little of the time	73	55.3%
	some of the time	38	28.8%
	good part of the time	12	9.1%
	most of the time	9	6.8%

i can breath in and out easily	a little of the time	31	23.5%
	some of the time	26	19.7%
	good part of the time	32	24.2%
	most of the time	43	32.6%
i get feelings of numbness and tingling in my fingers and toes	a little of the time	69	52.3%
	some of the time	36	27.3%
	good part of the time	19	14.4%
	most of the time	8	6.1%
i am bothered by stomach aches and indigestion	a little of the time	80	60.6%
	some of the time	27	20.5%
	good part of the time	17	12.9%
	most of the time	8	6.1%
i have to empty my bladder often	a little of the time	58	43.9%
	some of the time	40	30.3%
	good part of the time	20	15.2%
	most of the time	14	10.6%
my hands are usually dry and warm	a little of the time	53	40.2%
	some of the time	40	30.3%
	good part of the time	22	16.7%
	most of the time	17	12.9%
my face gets hot and blushes	a little of the time	65	49.2%
	some of the time	43	32.6%
	good part of the time	10	7.6%
	most of the time	14	10.6%
i fall a sleep easily and get a good night rest	a little of the time	47	35.6%
	some of the time	28	21.2%
	good part of the time	21	15.9%
	most of the time	36	27.3%
i have night mares	a little of the time	71	53.8%
	some of the time	37	28.0%
	good part of the time	9	6.8%
	most of the time		

 most of the time

15

11.4%

The Zung Self-Rating Anxiety Scale (SAS), created by Dr. Zung MD (1929–1992), is a self-administered tool comprising 20 items, of which 15 are positively worded and 5 are negatively worded. Respondents rated their experiences using four options: "A little of the time," "Some of the time," "Good part of the time," and "Most of the time." The detailed is given below.

Q1: I feel more nervous and anxious than usual

For that question, 47.0% (N = 62) of respondents answered "a little of the time," 40.9% (N = 54) answered "some of the time," 2.3% (N = 3) answered "a good part of the time," and 9.8% (N = 13) answered "most of the time."

Q2: I feel afraid for no reason at all.

For that question, 58.3% (N = 77) of respondents answered "a little of the time," 28% (N = 37) answered "some of the time," 11.4% (N = 15) answered "a good part of the time," and 2.3% (N = 3) answered "most of the time".

Q3. I get upset easily or feel panicky

For that question, 43.9% (N = 58) of respondents answered "a little of the time," 39.4% (N = 52) answered "some of the time," 10.6% (N = 14) answered "a good part of the time," and 6.1% (N = 8) answered "most of the time".

Q4. I feel like I'm falling apart and going to pieces.

For that question, 53.0% (N = 70) of respondents answered "a little of the time," 25.8% (N = 34) answered "some of the time," 9.8% (N = 13) answered "a good part of the time," and 11.4% (N = 5) answered "most of the time".

Q5. I feel that everything is all right and nothing bad will happen.

For that question, 28.5% (N = 35) of respondents answered "a little of the time," 31.1% (N = 41) answered "some of the time," 19.7% (N = 26) answered "a good part of the time," and 22.7% (N = 30) answered "most of the time".

Q6. My arms and legs shake and tremble

For that question, 58.8% (N = 75) of respondents answered "a little of the time," 30.3% (N = 40) answered "some of the time," 9.1% (N = 22) answered "a good part of the time," and 3.8% (N = 5) answered "most of the time".

Q7. I am bothered by headaches neck and back pain.

For that question, 47.0% (N = 62) of respondents answered "a little of the time," 33.3% (N = 44) answered "some of the time," 13.6% (N = 18) answered "a good part of the time," and 6.1% (N = 8) answered "most of the time".

Q8. I feel weak and get tired easily.

For that question, 39.4% (N = 52) of respondents answered "a little of the time," 40.2% (N = 53) answered "some of the time," 9.8% (N = 18) answered "a good part of the time," and 10.6% (N = 14) answered "most of the time".

Q9. I feel calm and can sit still easily.

For that question, 37.9% (N = 50) of respondents answered "a little of the time," 31.1% (N = 41) answered "some of the time," 19.7% (N = 26) answered "a good part of the time," and 11.4% (N = 15) answered "most of the time".

Q10. I can feel my heart beating fast.

For that question, 41.7% (N = 55) of respondents answered "a little of the time," 40.2% (N = 53) answered "some of the time," 9.8% (N = 13) answered "a good part of the time," and 8.3% (N = 11) answered "most of the time".

Q11. I am bothered by dizzy spells

For that question, 53.8% (N = 71) of respondents answered "a little of the time," 30.3% (N = 40) answered "some of the time," 9.8% (N = 13) answered "a good part of the time," and 6.1% (N = 8) answered "most of the time".

Q12. I have fainting spells or feel like it.

For that question, 66.3% (N = 76) of respondents answered "a little of the time," 28.8% (N = 38) answered "some of the time," 9.1% (N = 12) answered "a good part of the time," and 6.8% (N = 9) answered "most of the time".

Q13. I can breathe in and out easily.

For that question, 23.5% (N = 31) of respondents answered "a little of the time," 19.7% (N = 26) answered "some of the time," 24.2% (N = 32) answered "a good part of the time," and 32.6% (N = 43) answered "most of the time".

Q14. I get feelings of numbness and tingling in my fingers & toes.

For that question, 52.3% (N = 69) of respondents answered "a little of the time," 27.3% (N = 36) answered "some of the time," 14.4% (N = 19) answered "a good part of the time," and 6.1% (N = 8) answered "most of the time".

Q15. I am bothered by stomach aches or indigestion.

For that question, 60.6% (N = 80) of respondents answered "a little of the time," 20.5% (N = 36) answered "some of the time," 12.9% (N = 17) answered "a good part of the time," and 6.1% (N = 8) answered "most of the time".

Q16. I have to empty my bladder often.

For that question, 43.9% (N = 58) of respondents answered "a little of the time," 30.3% (N = 40) answered "some of the time," 15.2% (N = 20) answered "a good part of the time," and 10.6% (N = 14) answered "most of the time".

Q17. My hands are usually dry and warm.

For that question, 40.2% (N = 53) of respondents answered "a little of the time," 30.3% (N = 40) answered "some of the time," 16.7% (N = 22) answered "a good part of the time," and 12.9% (N = 17) answered "most of the time".

Q18. My face gets hot and blushes.

For that question, 49.2% (N = 65) of respondents answered "a little of the time," 32.6% (N = 43) answered "some of the time," 7.6% (N = 10) answered "a good part

of the time," and 10.6% (N = 14) answered "most of the time".

Q19. I fall asleep easily and get a good night's rest.

For that question, 35.6% (N = 47) of respondents answered "a little of the time," 21.2% (N = 28) answered "some of the time," 15.9% (N = 21) answered "a good part of the time," and 27.3% (N = 36) answered "most of the time".

Q20. I have nightmares.

For that question, 53.8% (N = 71) of respondents answered "a little of the time," 21.2% (N = 28) answered "some of the time," 6.8% (N = 9) answered "a good part of the time," and 11.4% (N = 15) answered "most of the time".

Table. 2.1: Frequency, percentage distribution, mean and standard deviation of level of anxiety among undergraduate nursing students.

Grading	Range of score	Frequency=n	Percent	Mean \pm SD
Valid	normal range	20-44	107	81.1
	mild to moderate	45-59	21	15.9
	severe anxiety	60-74	4	3.0
	extreme anxiety	Above 75	0	0
Total			132	100

Note: The maximum total score is =80 SD = standard deviation.

The data in Table 2.1 illustrates the mean anxiety levels among students. It indicates that 81.1% (N=107) of the students have a normal range of anxiety, while a smaller proportion, 15.9% (N=21), experience mild to moderate levels of anxiety. Only 3% (N=4) of the students fall outside these categories, with a Mean \pm SD of (1.22 \pm 0.49).

Figure 1: Distribution of Level of anxiety among final year BS Nursing students.

4.3 Association between Anxiety Levels and Selected Demographic Variables

To find out the association Chi-square test was done. To test the statistical significance the following null hypothesis was formulated

H₀: There is no significant association between the level of anxiety among the nursing students and selected demographic variable.

Table 3: Association between anxiety among the undergraduate nursing students and selected demographic variables

S.No	Variables	Chi-square value	p-value
1	Gender	1.057 ^a	0.589
2	Age	2.151 ^a	0.341
3	Area of residence	2.113 ^a	0.348
4	Name of institute	2.489 ^a	0.647
5	Type of family	2.298 ^a	0.317
6	Religion	3.823 ^a	0.430
7	Number of sibling	2.493 ^a	0.869
8	Income per month	9.339 ^a	0.155
9	Clinical experience	6.058 ^a	0.195
10	Experience of caring the sick	1.181 ^a	0.554
11	Relative in medical field	3.193 ^a	0.203

*P < 0.05 (*significant)

The findings presented in Table 3 indicate that there was no significant association

between anxiety and any of the selected demographic variables. These variables included gender, age, area of residence, type of institute, family type, religion, number of siblings, monthly income, clinical experience in caring for sick individuals, and having relatives working in the medical profession. As a result, the research hypothesis was rejected for all the demographic variables considered in the study.

Chapter 5: Discussion and Conclusion

5.1 Discussion

Anxiety, often triggered by unfamiliar environments and fear of mistakes, significantly impacts nursing students during clinical placements⁽²⁾. This anxiety can hinder learning and patient care, with higher levels observed in clinical settings, particularly in the US⁽⁸⁾. To support the development of confident and skilled professionals, addressing clinical anxiety among nursing students is essential. This study aimed to assess the level of anxiety among final-year nursing students to better understand the factors contributing to their anxiety. By identifying these factors, the study seeks to propose strategies for reducing anxiety and enhancing student outcomes in clinical settings.

The present study revealed that the mean anxiety level of students showed that 81.1% of the students had a normal range of anxiety, 15.9% had mild to moderate levels of anxiety, and only 3% experienced severe anxiety, with a Mean \pm SD of 1.22 ± 0.49 . These findings align with a study that assessed anxiety levels among 100 nursing students using survey questionnaires and the Zung Self-Rating Anxiety Scale. This study found that 83% of the students experienced a normal level of anxiety, while 17% had mild to moderate levels, with a Mean \pm SD of 1.17 ± 0.318 ⁽⁵⁾. Another study conducted during psychiatry clinical rotations indicated that 67.7% of students had a normal range of anxiety, while 32.3% experienced mild to moderate levels of anxiety⁽¹⁹⁾. Similarly, a study on clinical experiences reported that 11.3% of nursing students experienced severe anxiety, 32.1% had moderate anxiety, and 53.8% had mild anxiety⁽²⁰⁾. In a study conducted among baccalaureate nursing students in Hong Kong, China, the prevalence of anxiety was found to be 39.9%⁽¹⁴⁾. Another study reported that 61.1% of nursing students experienced mild levels of anxiety related to hospital training⁽⁷⁾.

Additionally, it was observed that undergraduate nursing students were prone to anxiety during the later stages of their clinical internships, with specific sources of anxiety including career decision-making, job pursuit, graduation, and licensure examinations⁽¹¹⁾. Nursing students are also known to experience heightened anxiety levels when providing patient care during clinical rotations. The use of simulation as a teaching strategy has been shown to effectively reduce anxiety for both clinicians and nursing students⁽⁶⁾. Another study identified seven key factors influencing nursing students' clinical learning experiences. These factors included the role of an

expert clinical instructor, the supportive role of clinical nurses, effective communication and relationships, clear job descriptions, theory-practice integration, availability of resources, and social and psychological factors⁽¹⁵⁾. Furthermore, it was found that problems encountered in clinical settings had a significant negative impact on both anxiety levels and motivation. Addressing these problems is critical for reducing anxiety and increasing motivation among nursing students.⁽⁴⁾

The findings from this study, in conjunction with the existing literature, emphasize the need for targeted interventions to reduce clinical anxiety and create a supportive environment that fosters the development of confident and skilled nursing professionals.

5.2 Conclusion

The majority of students (81.1%) had a normal range of anxiety, while (15.9%) had experienced mild to moderate anxiety levels, and only (3%) had severe anxiety, with a Mean \pm SD of (1.22 \pm 0.49). A Chi-square test was conducted to assess the association between anxiety and selected demographic variables, including gender, age, area of residence, institute, family type, religion, monthly income, number of siblings, clinical experience in caring for the sick, and having relatives in the medical profession. The results showed no significant association between anxiety and any of these demographic variables, leading to the rejection of the research hypothesis for all demographic factors. The study concluded that the teaching and training provided to nursing students before their clinical experience were adequate and appropriate.

5.3 Limitations

- ❖ The study relied on a self-selected sample, so data from non-respondents could not be collected, potentially introducing selection bias and limiting the representativeness of the findings.
- ❖ The small sample size limits the generalizability of the study's findings to the broader population of final-year BS Nursing students.
- ❖ The research was restricted to assessing the level of anxiety without implementing any interventions to address or reduce the anxiety identified.

5.4 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are suggested for future research:

- ❖ Conducting studies with larger sample sizes to improve the generalizability of the results.
- ❖ Implementing interventional research to address and mitigate anxiety among nursing students.
- ❖ Undertaking comparative studies to evaluate anxiety levels in various hospital settings.
- ❖ Investigating factors that promote effective learning in clinical environments.

REFERENCES

1. Abas NQ. Assessing the Anxiety Level in Nursing Students at the Commencement of their Academic Year. 2017;21(1):37–41.
2. Sun F ko, Long A, Shan Y, Huang H man, You J hui, Chiang C ying. Nurse Education Today Undergraduate student nurses ' lived experiences of anxiety during their fi rst clinical practicum: A phenomenological study. YNEDT [Internet]. 2016;37:21–6. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2015.11.001>
3. Al-ghareeb A, Mckenna L, Cooper S. International Journal of Nursing Studies The in fl uence of anxiety on student nurse performance in a simulated clinical setting : A mixed methods design. Int J Nurs Stud [Internet]. 2019;98:57–66. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2019.06.006>
4. Yildirim TA, Dalcali BK. The Effect of Nursing Students ' Problems in the Clinical Practice Environment on Anxiety Level and Motivation. 2020;13(3):2054–63.
5. Lavina R, Deepa P, Abin K, Shwetha R, Priya MN. Anxiety Among the Nursing Students During the Initial Clinical Experience. Int J Curr Res Rev. 2021;13(14):161–5.
6. Hollenbach PM. Research Brief. 2016;37(1):45–7.
7. Ahmed FA, Alrashidi N, Mohamed RA, Asiri A, Ali A Al, Aly KH, et al. Satisfaction and anxiety level during clinical training among nursing students. BMC Nurs [Internet]. 2023;1–11. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-023-01352-3>
8. Cornine A. An Integrative Review. 2020;41(4):229–34.
9. Simpson M claude G, Sawatzky J ann V. Nurse Education Today Clinical placement anxiety in undergraduate nursing students : A concept analysis. Nurse Educ Today [Internet]. 2020;87(December 2019):104329. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2019.104329>
10. Curtis A, Sagong H. Nursing students ' perceptions of older adults , confidence , and anxiety level changes with their first clinical rotation: A descriptive pilot study. 2024;2(3).
11. Yi QF, Yan J, Zhang CJ, Yang GL, Huang H, Yang Y. The experience of anxiety among Chinese undergraduate nursing students in the later period of their internships: findings from a qualitative study. BMC Nurs [Internet]. 2022;1–10. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-022-00847-9>
12. Chernomas WM, Shapiro C. Stress , Depression , and Anxiety among Undergraduate Nursing Students. 2013;10(1):255–66.
13. Kroning BM. Strategies for Improving Nursing Students' Mental Health Clinical Rotation. 2019;(July 2016).

14. Cheung T, Wong SY, Wong KY, Law LY, Ng K. Depression , Anxiety and Symptoms of Stress among Baccalaureate Nursing Students in Hong Kong : A Cross-Sectional Study.
15. Rozario MD, Begum D, Costa ND, Nasrin M. Perception and Experiences of Undergraduate Nursing Students on Clinical Learning Environment in a Public University. 2022;244–51.
16. Alshahrani Y, Cusack L, Prof AA, Rasmussen P. Nurse Education Today Undergraduate nursing students ' strategies for coping with their fi rst clinical placement: Descriptive survey study. Nurse Educ Today [Internet]. 2018;69(July):104–8. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2018.07.005>
17. Admi H, Moshe-eilon Y, Sharon D, Mann M. Nurse Education Today Nursing students ' stress and satisfaction in clinical practice along di ff erent stages : A cross-sectional study ☆. Nurse Educ Today [Internet]. 2018;68(May):86–92. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2018.05.027>
18. Bektas I, Rn SS, Rn IC. The predict of metacognitive awareness of nursing students on self - confidence and anxiety in clinical decision - making. 2020;(August):1–6.
19. Words K. Pakistan biomedical journal. 2023;6(November):23–7.
20. Iqbal S. Nursing Students ' Anxiety Related to Clinical Experiences. 2017;3(9):111–5.